

Studies in Copper(II) Chelates. Part VII. Mixed Chelates with Tridentate dibasic Hydrazone Schiff Bases and α, α' -dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline)

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Copper(II) mixed chelates containing a tridentate dibasic hydrazone Schiff base and dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline) have been prepared. These are believed to possess polymeric, distorted octahedral structures. Reactions of these chelates in donor solvents have been studied. Their electronic spectra have only one absorption band in the visible region around 16kK, and they show normal magnetic moments at room temperature.

OXO-VANADIUM(IV) mixed chelates containing a tridentate dibasic hydrazone Schiff base and dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline) have been reported¹. We now describe similar mixed chelates of copper(II). The Schiff bases ($LH_2(I)$ or $L'H_2(II)$) employed in this study are the condensation products of a hydroxyaldehyde (salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde or 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde) or *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with benzoyl hydrazide (or *o*-hydroxybenzoylhydrazide).

Experimental

Benzoylhydrazide², *o*-hydroxybenzoylhydrazide³, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde⁴, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone⁵ were prepared by following standard procedures. The

Schiff bases were obtained by refluxing equimolar quantities of the hydrazide and the aldehyde in ethanol on a steam bath.

General procedure of syntheses of the mixed chelates :

Copper(II) acetate dihydrate (0.001 mole in 30 ml. ethanol) and dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline, 0.001 mole in 10 ml ethanol) were mixed and warmed on a steam bath. To the resulting deep blue solution was added a solution of the Schiff base (0.001 mole in 40 ml ethanol) and the mixture refluxed for 1-2 hrs. Green, olive green or yellow crystals separated. These were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in air.

The ligand obtained from salicylaldehyde and *o*-hydroxybenzoylhydrazide (LH₂(I); X = H; Y = *o*-OH) (0.001 mole), being sparingly soluble in ethanol, was dissolved in 150 ml ethanol. After the reaction with copper(II) acetate, and dipyriddy (or *o*-phenanthroline) and the above Schiff base was over, volume was reduced, the solution cooled and the mixed chelates treated as described above.

In the case of the ligands of the type L'H₂(II) (X = H; Y = H or *o*-OH) small amount of the copper(II) complex of the Schiff base alone separated initially. The green precipitate was filtered after about 10 min. and the filtrate refluxed to obtain the desired mixed chelates.

Reactions of the mixed chelates in donor solvents :

The mixed chelates were refluxed in pyridine (Py), γ -picoline (γ -pic) or dimethylformamide (DMF) whereby a brown solution was obtained. This was filtered, treated with alcohol and crystallised.

Magnetic measurements were obtained for solid samples by the Gouy method using A.R. CuSO₄·5H₂O as calibrant. Magnetic moment was calculated from the relation :

$$\mu_{eff} = 2.84\sqrt{\chi_M^{corr} \times T} \text{ BM}$$

where the symbols carry usual significance. Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants⁶.

Absorption spectra were recorded with Hilger-Waats UVISPEK Spectrophotometer using 1 cm cell. Conductance was measured at 10⁻³M in DMF. The chelates were ignited to copper oxide which was then estimated iodometrically. Nitrogen was determined by combustion. The characterisation data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis of the mixed chelates: Two straight forward routes are conceivable: (1) reacting the dimeric antiferromagnetic square planar copper(II) complex of the tridentate Schiff bases with dipyriddy (or *o*-phenanthroline); (2) reacting copper(II) complex of dipyriddy (or *o*-phenanthroline) obtained, *in situ* ([Cu(dipy)aq]X₂ etc.) with the tridentate dibasic Schiff bases. Both these routes worked for copper (II) mixed chelates containing dipyriddy (or *o*-phenanthroline) and tridentate dibasic salicylaldene amino-acid Schiff bases⁷. In this present study method (1) did not work possibly due to the extreme insolubility of the dimeric antiferromagnetic species in common organic solvents. In the case of the Schiff bases derived from *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, even method (2) led to a partial separation of the copper(II) complexes of the Schiff base alone. Method (2) did not also work for the mixed chelates containing dipyriddy and LH₂(I) (X = 5, 6 benzo; Y = H). We attempted to synthesise this complex *via* reaction of dipyriddy on the pyridino complex [Cu(Py)(L)] (LH₂(I)):

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF COPPER(II) MIXED CHELATES

LH ₂	Colour	% of Cu		% of N	
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L or L')]					
X = 5,6-benzo; Y = H	dark yellow crystalline	11.9	11.58	10.5	10.36
X = H; Y = H	black powder	13.19	13.17	11.6	10.05
X = 5-Cl; Y = H	black powder	12.3	12.1	10.8	9.94
X = 5-NO ₂ ; Y = H	green, crystalline	12.03	12.00	1.6	11.1
X = OH; Y = H	green powder	12.7	12.66	11.1	11.44
X = 5,6-benzo; Y = OH	yellow powder	11.6	11.56	10.2	10.7
X = H; Y = OH	green shining crystals	12.7	12.5	11.2	10.96
X = 5-Cl; Y = OH	yellow powder	11.9	11.7	10.5	10.3
L'H ₂					
X = H; Y = H	black shining crystals	12.8	12.67	11.3	11.56
X = H; Y = OH	deep green shining crystals	12.4	12.05	10.9	10.7
LH ₂ [Cu(dipy)(L or L')]					
X = H; Y = H	black powder	13.9	13.88	12.2	12.64
X = 5-Cl; Y = H	deep brown shining crystals	12.9	12.6	11.4	11.08
X = 5-NO ₂ ; Y = H	green, crystalline	12.6	12.7	11.18	11.8
X = OH; Y = H	green powder	13.4	13.07	11.9	11.6
X = 5,6-benzo; Y = OH	yellow powder	12.1	11.9	10.7	10.61
X = 5-Cl; Y = OH	yellow powder	12.4	12.15	11.02	10.95
L'H ₂					
X = H; Y = H	black shining crystals	13.4	13.1	11.9	12.15
X = H; Y = OH	deep green shining crystals	12.8	12.5	11.5	11.36

(X = 5,6 benzo; Y = H). Unfortunately this too led to no success. The mixed chelates are anhydrous and are green, olive green or yellow in colour.

Reactions of the mixed chelates : Reactions of these mixed chelates in donor solvents have revealed several features : (1) the chelated heterocyclic ligand may be knocked off in some cases and replaced by one molecule of pyridine, γ -picoline or dimethylformamide, (2) the coordinated pyridine etc. can be substituted by dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline), (3) pyridine, γ -picoline can be introduced in some cases in addition to the other two chelated ligands, (4) the pyridino complex can be made to lose the pyridine by heating in the solid state or under reflux in ethanol, (5) some mixed chelates remain unaffected by the donor solvent. The reaction products were identified by elemental analysis, decomposition temperature and microscopic examination. Relevant data are given in Table 2. However, we have not been able to discover a rational view of these reactions. The reactions of one mixed chelate [Cu(*o*-phen)(L)] (LH₂(I); X = 5,6 benzo; Y = H) are shown in Chart 1.

Conductivity and Molecular weights : The complexes are all non-electrolytes in DMF (Table 3). The non-electrolytic nature rules out any alternative formulation such as [Cu(dipy)₂][Cu(L)₂] or [Cu(*o*-phen)₂][Cu(L)₂]. The samples are insoluble in common organic non-donor solvents. They dissolve in coordinating solvents alone. The insolubility of the present chelates frustrated all attempts towards molecular weight determinations. Several substitutions were made in the aldehyde and the hydrazide moieties in the hope of obtaining a benzene or bromoform soluble species. But these substitutions did not imbibe in the mixed chelates the desired solubility. Out of our frustrations we made several attempts of molecular weight determinations in molten camphor. The range of solubility of the chelates in camphor and the resulting depression were such that determinations could not be considered conclusive. However, these studies pointed to a concentration dependence of the molecular weight. A polymeric structure of the mixed chelates suggests itself. The Schiff base oxygen atoms are presumably coordinated in addition to its own copper(II), to a second copper(II) of another molecule⁸ and so on

TABLE 2—REACTIONS OF [Cu(*o*-phen/dipy)(L)].

Reactants*	L	Product	Analysis of the product**		
			% of Cu	% of N	% of loss
[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)] alone	X = 5,6-benzo; Y = H	—	11.58(11.9)**	10.36(10.5)	—
[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)] + Py	"	[Cu(Py)(L)]	14.7(14.6)	9.7(9.5)	18.3(18.1)
[Cu(Py)(L) + <i>o</i> -phen in refluxing alcohol	"	[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)]	11.58(11.9)	10.36(10.5)	—
[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)] + γ -pic	"	[Cu(γ -pic)(L)]	14.2(13.9)	—	20.9(20.5)
[Cu(γ -pic)(L)] + <i>o</i> -phen in refluxing alcohol	"	[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)]	11.58(11.9)	10.36(10.5)	—
[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)] + DMF	"	[Cu(DMF)(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)]	10.5(10.9)	11.7(11.7)	—
[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)] alone	X = 5,6-benzo; Y = OH	—	11.6(11.56)	10.7(10.2)	—
[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)] + Py	"	No reaction	—	—	—
[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)] + γ -pic	"	No reaction	—	—	—
[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)] + DMF	"	[Cu(DMF)(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)]	10.2(10.23)	11.2(11.2)	—
[Cu(dipy)(L)] alone	"	—	11.9(12.1)	10.61(10.7)	—
[Cu(dipy)(L)] + Py	"	[Cu(Py)(L)]	14.2(14.1)	9.4(9.8)	17.6(17.1)
[Cu(Py)(L)] + dipy in refluxing alcohol	"	[Cu(dipy)(L)]	11.9(12.1)	10.61(10.7)	—
[Cu(dipy)(L)] + γ -pic	"	[Cu(γ -pic)(L)]	(13.9)14.1	(9.8)9.4	20.7(20.5)
[Cu(γ -pic)(L)] + dipy in refluxing alcohol	"	[Cu(dipy)(L)]	11.9(12.1)	10.61(10.7)	—

* The mixed chelates were refluxed in appropriate solvents.

** Calculated values are in parentheses.

TABLE 3—MAGNETIC MOMENT AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compounds	L or L'	$\chi_{Mcorr} \times 10^{-6}$	μ_{eff}	T°(K)	Conductivity (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹) in DMF at 25°
[Cu(o-phen)(L)]	X = 5,6-benzo; Y = H	1363	1.82	302	~1
[Cu(o-phen)(L)]	X = H; Y = H	1190	1.70	298	~1
[Cu(o-phen)(L)]	X = 5-Cl; Y = H	1220	1.71	300	~1
[Cu(dipy)(L)]	X = 5-Cl; Y = H	1220	1.72	302	~1
[Cu(o-phen)(L)]	X = OH; Y = H	1295	1.77	303	~2
[Cu(dipy)(L)]	X = OH; Y = H	1209	1.72	305	—
[Cu(Py)(L)]	X = 5,6-benzo; Y = H	1276	1.75	300	—
[Cu(o-phen)(L)]	X = H; Y = OH	—	—	—	~2
[Cu(dipy)(L)]	X = H; Y = OH	—	—	—	~1
[Cu(o-phen)(L)]	X = 5-Cl; Y = OH	1186	1.70	305	~1
[Cu(dipy)(L)]	X = 5-Cl; Y = OH	1305	1.78	303	—
[Cu(o-phen)(L')]	X = H; Y = H	—	—	—	~2

(Fig. 1). However, such polymeric structure does not permit strong copper(II)—copper(II) interaction *via* oxygen since the room temperature magnetic

Fig. 1. Two suggested structures for [Cu(dipy)(L)] or [Cu(o-phen)(L)].

(a) a dimeric species; (b) a polymeric species.

N-N = dipy/o-phen;

O-N-O = tridentate dibasic Schiff base anion.

moments are but normal. N,N' ethylene bis(salicylaldiminato) copper(II) is known to be dimeric in the solid crystalline state⁹ *via* Cu-O intermolecular bonds. However, this link must be weak since no significant magnetic exchange interaction¹⁰ between neighbouring Cu(II) atoms is known, presumably because the Cu-O bonds are appreciably long. Dissolution of the mixed chelates in donor solvents indicates the breakdown of the polymeric species.

Magnetic moments: These complexes show paramagnetic spin only moments 1.70 to 1.82 BM (Table 3) at room temperature. The magnetic moments of octahedral copper(II) complexes are ~1.9 B.M. Square planar complexes have lower magnetic moments than the octahedral complexes¹¹. The copper(II) complexes under study are believed to have distorted octahedral configuration.

Infrared spectra: The important infrared spectral bands and their assignments (Table 4) are based on a study of the free Schiff bases, the mixed chelates, [Cu(dipy)Cl₂] and [Cu(o-phen)Cl₂]. Understandably there are several regions, for example aromatic vibrations and the C=N stretch which are overlapping in the coordinated Schiff bases and in the coordinated heterocycles. The strong bands at ~730, 1170 and 1420 cm⁻¹ do not appear in the Schiff bases but appear both in the [Cu(dipy)Cl₂] or [Cu(o-phen)Cl₂] and the mixed chelates. A perusal of Table 4 will show that both the tridentate Schiff base and the heterocyclic ligand are coordinated to the metal ion. Inskeep¹² has claimed that below 600 cm⁻¹ region the o-phenanthroline or dipyriddy complexes have several characteristic features useful for identification of coordinated ligands. Below 600 cm⁻¹ the intensity of the absorption bands in our complexes was not strong enough to be of any diagnostic value. The infrared spectra of the Schiff base ligands reveal bands of strong or medium intensity around 1650–1660 cm⁻¹ and 1595–1620 cm⁻¹ indicating C=O and C=N stretching frequencies respectively. Sterk and Ziegler¹³ assign the bands at 1656 and 1625 cm⁻¹ to the C=O and C=N stretching vibrations respectively, while Hardzi¹⁴ attributes only the latter to the C=O vibration. The lowering of the C=N stretching frequency is an indication of the coordination of imine nitrogen atom. Absence of C=O stretching mode in the mixed chelates indicates that the metal has coordinated in the imidol form LH₂(Ib) or L'H₂(IIb) of the Schiff bases. All the Schiff base ligands have strong bands at ~3285, 3170 cm⁻¹ characteristic of the N-H vibrations, these being comparable to

TABLE 4—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF LIGANDS AND MIXED COMPLEXES (in cm^{-1})

Ligand/complex	dipy/o-phen	$\nu\text{C} = \text{O}$	$\nu\text{C} = \text{N}$	νNH
$[\text{LH}_2]$ (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = H)	—	1640 s	1620 m 1600 w	3200 m
$[\text{Cu}(o\text{-phen})(\text{L})]$ (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = H)	725 msh 1185 s 1425 s	—	1610 s 1595 s	—
$[\text{LH}_2]$ (X = OH; Y = H)	—	1650 s	1595 m 1610 s	3225 s
$[\text{Cu}(o\text{-phen})(\text{L})]$ (X = OH; Y = H)	715 m 1170 w 1415 m	—	1590 vs	—
$[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{L})]$ (X = OH; Y = H)	725 w 1170 wb 1425 s	—	1600 vs	—
$[\text{LH}_2]$ (X = H; Y = H)	—	1670 ssh 1660 msh	1615 w 1605 wsh	3270 m
$[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{L})]$ (X = H; Y = H)	735 m 1165 m 1430 sh	—	1602 s	—
$[\text{LH}_2]$ (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = OH)	—	1650 ssh	1600 ssh	3210 wb
$[\text{Cu}(o\text{-phen})(\text{L})]$ (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = OH)	715 s 1180 m 1425 m	—	1600 vs	—
$[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{L})]$ (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = OH)	725 m 1185 s 1375 s	—	1595 s	—

$[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_2]$ has bands at 1440 vs, 1167 s, 730 s cm^{-1} and

$[\text{Cu}(o\text{-phen})\text{Cl}_2]$ shows bands at 1420 s, 1195 wsh, 735 m cm^{-1} .

s = strong; m = medium; w = weak; b = broad; vs = very strong; sh = shoulder.

TABLE 5—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA FOR COPPER(II) MIXED CHELATES

Compounds	State	Colour in solution	Absorption bands in kK	ϵ max
$[\text{Cu}(o\text{-phen})(\text{L})]$ (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = H)	Pyridine	green	16.1—15.8	134
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Py})(\text{L})]$ (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = H)	Reflectance	—	18.0—13.0 b	—
	Pyridine	green	16.1 b	150
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L})]$ (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = H)	Reflectance	—	17.0—18.0 b	—
	Pyridine	green	16.4—16.1 b	140
$[\text{Cu}(o\text{-phen})(\text{L})]$ (X = H; Y = H)	Reflectance	—	14.8	—
	Pyridine	deep green	16.4—16.1 sh	148
$[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{L})]$ (X = H; Y = H)	Pyridine	dark green	16.0	132
	Reflectance	—	15.0—13.2 b	—
$[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{L})]$ (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = OH)	Pyridine	dark green	15.8—15.6 b	136
	Dioxane	dark yellow	16.3	138
$[\text{Cu}(o\text{-phen})(\text{L})]$ (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = OH)	Pyridine	yellow	15.8 sh	156
	Dioxane	dark yellow	16.9	166
$[\text{Cu}(\text{Py})(\text{L})]$ (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = OH)	Pyridine	dark green	15.4—15.3	138
	Pyridine	green	15.8—15.6 b	136
$[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{L})]$ (X = 5-Cl; Y = H)	Pyridine	green	15.8—15.6 b	132
$[\text{Cu}(o\text{-phen})(\text{L})]$ (X = 5-Cl; Y = OH)	Pyridine	green	15.6—15.3 b	56
$[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{L})]$ (X = 5-Cl; Y = OH)	Pyridine	green	15.6—15.3 b	52

b = broad; sh = shoulder.

the N-H stretches observed in benzoyl hydrazide¹⁵ (at ~ 3285 s, 3170s, cm^{-1}). Thus structure $\text{LH}_2(\text{Ia})$ and $\text{L}'\text{H}_2(\text{IIa})$ for the solid Schiff bases are established. In the mixed chelates these bands are missing which supports the Schiff bases acting in the imidol forms (Ib; IIb) in the complexes. The non-electrolytic nature of the mixed chelates and the sizes of the two rings formed at the metal also support this view.

Electronic spectra: The reflectance spectrum of the Schiff base complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})]$ ($\text{LH}_2(\text{I}); \text{X} = 5,6$

benzo; Y = H) shows a band at ~ 14.8 kK. It is well known that copper(II) complexes of tridentate dibasic Schiff bases (ONO donor set) are dimeric and antiferromagnetic¹⁶. Thus 14.8kK band of our $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})]$ may be taken as characteristic of square planar $[\text{CuNO}_3]$ chromophore, the ligand field strength of similar terminal and bridging ligand being nearly the same¹⁷. This antiferromagnetic compound gives in donor solvents (such as pyridine) $[\text{Cu}(\text{Py})(\text{L})]$, the reflectance spectrum of which has a broad shoulder at 17–18kK. Chloroform spectrum of ethylene bis

(salicylaldiminato) copper(II) with a similar chromophore has an absorption band around 17.5kK. A recent study¹⁸ of copper(II) pyrazine carboxylate also gives a band at ~16.5kK as due to the square planar $[\text{CuN}_2\text{O}_2]$ chromophore. However, the spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})]$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{Py})(\text{L})]$ and $[\text{Cu}(o\text{-phen})(\text{L})]$ in pyridine are almost the same (Fig. 2). This strikingly shows that in donor solvent the effective ligand field environment around copper(II) must be the same, and the most likely chromophore is a distorted octahedral

Fig. 2. Electronic spectra of some copper(II) mixed chelates.

- I $[\text{Cu}(o\text{-phen})(\text{L})]$, (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = H) in pyridine.
 II $[\text{Cu}(\text{Py})(\text{L})]$, (X = 5,6-benzo; Y = H) in pyridine.
 III $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})]$, (X = 5,6 benzo; Y = H) in pyridine.
 IV, V, and VI are the solid reflectance spectra of I, II and III respectively.

$[\text{CuN}_4\text{O}_2]$. Although copper(II) complexes with $[\text{CuN}_4\text{O}_2]$ chromophore may absorb over a quite wide range¹⁹, a band in the neighbourhood of 16kK has been suggested as a reasonable test of the presence of this chromophore²⁰. A six coordinate complex diaquo bis(2-acetamidopyridine) copper(II) $[\text{CuN}_4\text{O}_2]$ chromophore] has an absorption band at 16.4kK²¹. The mixed chelates $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})\text{X}_2]$, $[\text{Cu}(o\text{-phen})(\text{BigH})\text{X}_2]$ in aqueous medium where the same chromophore is presumably present also showed broad absorption band at ~15.6–16.9kK²². The band around 15.6–16.1kK in the complexes reported herein points to a distorted octahedral $[\text{CuN}_4\text{O}_2]$ chromophore. In the solid state our mixed chelates are really not monomeric five coordinate $[\text{CuN}_3\text{O}_2]$ as is revealed by their extreme insolubility in all common solvents; instead these are $[\text{CuN}_3\text{O}_2]_n$ through polymerisation via bridging oxygen atoms. Finally we wish to emphasize that our spectral measurements (Table 5) would not distinguish as to whether or not the chelated heterocycles, dipy or o-phen, is replaced by pyridine in pyridine solvent. On refluxing quite a few undergo substitution by pyridine.

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